

**EXTENT OF STAKEHOLDERS' INVOLVEMENT IN SCHOOL PROGRAMS AS
CORRELATE TO SCHOOL PERFORMANCE: BASIS FOR AN
INTERVENTION PROGRAM**

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Extent of Stakeholders' Involvement in School Programs as Correlate to School Performance: Basis for an Intervention Program

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Abstract

This study aimed to determine the extent of stakeholders' involvement in school programs as correlate to the performance of Barangka Elementary School, District I, Division of Marikina City during the school year 2022-2023. The method of research used was the descriptive correlational type with the survey questionnaire as the data gathering instrument which was answered by the respondents through google forms and hard copy checklist. The respondents of the study were the internal stakeholders composed of one school head, three non-teaching personnel, 11 pupils or officers of the Supreme Pupil Government and 50 teachers and 65 external stakeholders composed of eight barangay officials as representatives of the local government unit, three representatives from the Non-Government Organizations, four representatives from the BES alumni officers, and 50 parents. It was found out that the extent of the stakeholders' involvement in the key school programs as perceived by the internal and external stakeholders was moderate. Likewise, the level of performance of Barangka Elementary School as perceived by the two groups of stakeholder respondents in terms of access was very high and moderate in terms of quality and governance from the internal and external stakeholders. Furthermore, there was a significant correlation between the extent of the internal and external stakeholders' involvement in the school programs and school performance. Based on the findings of the study, an intervention program "Stakeholders Engagement Program" was proposed and developed to improve and strengthen the stakeholder's involvement in school programs.

Keywords: *stakeholder's involvement, school programs, school performance, intervention program*

Introduction

In education, the term stakeholder typically refers to anyone who is invested in the welfare and success of a school and its students, including administrators, teachers, staff members, students, parents, families, community members, local business leaders and elected officials such as municipal and barangay officials. In fact, the stakeholders have the significant responsibility of leading and supporting the learners and in creating an enjoyable environment so that their potential and self-confidence can be well developed.

Additionally, in stakeholders lie the resources, information, and opportunities, the love, care and wisdom needed to support the goals of the education system. As a matter of fact, Dep-Ed explained the roles and responsibilities of stakeholders in school in crafting the School Improvement Plan (SIP) as cited in DepEd Order No. 23 (i.e., stakeholders are members of the working committee who investigates their involvement in making the school conducive to learning). They are also responsible for the achievement of the learning outcomes through their active participation in school activities, programs and projects.

An article written by a principal in Pampanga explained that stakeholders play an important role in managing the school. They are the partners of the school leaders in making the school conducive to teaching and learning. The external stakeholders are included as members of the evaluating team to evaluate the SBM level of practice. She added that stakeholders are now integral part of the school system. Thus, the school strengthens their linkages with the stakeholders in the community to win their support.

To create effective education system and effective environments, DepEd enjoins all stakeholders that there is a need to come together in a meaningful way through collaboration and therefore connection. And successful collaboration between all stakeholders means deep listening as well as active doing (Google, Nov. 4, 2020).

To sum up, each stakeholder in education plays a unique role and can help increase support for educational goals. Their involvement in education plays an important part, as the purpose of each stakeholder is to reach a common educational goal through team effort. When a multiple of stakeholders are engaged, the team effort increases the chances of success in reaching these goals. Therefore, a team effort on the part of stakeholders is involved in achieving educational goals.

With the foregoing discussions, the researcher thinks that there is a need to determine the actual stakeholder's involvement in school programs that influences and have an impact to the school performance so that the stakeholders' involvement in school programs and projects can be continuously enhanced, strengthened, and as well recognized.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the extent of stakeholder's involvement in the implementation of school programs as correlate to the performance of Barangka Elementary School, District I, Division of Marikina City during the school year 2022-2023. Specifically, it sought answers to the following questions:

1. What is the extent of the stakeholders' involvement in the key school programs as perceived by internal and external

stakeholders in terms of the following aspects:

- 1.1. Planning
- 1.2. Decision making
- 1.3. Information dissemination
- 1.4. Implementation
- 1.5. Engagement strategy
- 1.6. Evaluation
2. Is there a significant difference between the perceptions of the groups of mentioned key school programs?
3. What is the level of school performance of Barangka Elementary School as perceived by internal and external stakeholders in terms of:
 - 3.1. Access;
 - 3.2. Quality; and
 - 3.3. Governance
4. Is there a significant correlation between the extent of the internal and external stakeholders' involvement in the school programs and school performance?
5. What are the challenges encountered by the internal and external stakeholders in the implementation of the school programs as perceived by the two groups of respondents?
6. Based on the findings of the study, what intervention program may be proposed to Improve and strengthen stakeholders' involvement in school programs designed to enhance and sustain the effective and quality performance of Barangka Elementary School?

Literature Review

Watts (2023) explained that each stakeholder in education plays a unique role and can help increase support for educational goals. According to her the stakeholder's involvement in education plays an important part because the purpose of each stakeholder is to reach a common educational goal through team effort that when multiple stakeholders are engaged, the team effort increases the chances of success in reaching these goals.

In addition, in Ronahlayne's (2021) article, she explained that behind a well-planned curriculum, it goes through a process of change which happens in implementing a curriculum. Furthermore, according to her the success of a curriculum lies within those individuals working on its progress and innovation that through their collaborative efforts, curriculum implementation happens to be effective and efficient. According to her these individuals or institutions are called stakeholders who are part of curriculum process, and they are associated with the welfare and success of a school and its students therefore the role as stakeholders is crucial.

Likewise, the article of Ashqar et al. (2020) analyzed the case-study of Israeli stakeholders' reaction to the Israeli students' performance in the PISA test. Their argument in the article is that the media in Israel deals extensively with the performance of Israeli students in their tests, and the media turns into the main source that feeds Israeli parents' knowledge of the test results. Pressure was employed by parents in particular on the government and schools to do all in their capacity to improve the results and to raise Israel's ranking on these international tests. Therefore, as a result, the government has created a commission to reform the education system.

On the other hand, the article of De Torres (2021) was presented with the aim of determining stakeholders' engagement to students' self-learning during the pandemic with the end view of proposing a creative learning environment for the learners that participation of stakeholders to students' self-learning during the transition from teacher-learning responsibilities to student-learning responsibilities.

The first reviewed study was that of Ochunga et al. (2017) which focused on the influence of stakeholders' participation on sustainability of community development projects. It was found out that that there was a weak but significant negative association between passive participation among stakeholders and sustainability of community development projects.

The research study of Gamede et al. (2021) reviewed the impact of stakeholder's participation due to the learner's poor academic performance, lack of qualified teachers which led to poor teaching and learning, lack of resources and poor infrastructure of the rural school's education in South Africa. n the result of the study, it was found out that the reasons for poor academic performances of learners in rural areas of South Africa could be attributed to various factors, that the role and active participation of rural education stakeholders in salvaging the situation.

Additionally, the research conducted by Sattar et al. (2022) which was to extend this line of inquiry has linked stakeholders' participation, goal directness and classroom context with students' academic outcomes. The role of parents, teachers, peers and students (themselves) remained significant even though stakeholders' participation caused low variance in students' academic performance.

Moreover, De Vera (2022) researched on the participation of stakeholders and its relationship to the implementation of school-based management of their school. The results showed that the extent of participation of the stakeholders along school governance, curriculum implementation, community involvement, and pupils' activities was high with. Furthermore, the respondents' assessment of the level of implementation of school-based management (SBM) in BEES was low.

Methodology

Research Design

The descriptive-correlational method of research was used in this study since it tried to collect and analyze data on the extent of stakeholder’s involvement in in school programs and the performance of the school and also explained the relationship between the two variables.

Canonizado (2020) cited that the aim of descriptive-correlational method is to understand and assess the statistical relationship between the two variables with no influence from any extraneous variable. He also added that this kind of research method is also useful to establish a link or influence of one variable from another variable.

Respondents

The data of this study was obtained from 65 internal stakeholders which consisted of one school head, 50 teachers , three non- teaching personnel, and 11 pupils/officers of the Supreme Pupil Government and also 65 external stakeholders which consisted of 48 parents, eight barangay officials, three non-government organization representatives, and six alumni who answered the questionnaire in relation to the stakeholders involvement as correlate to school performance.

Instrument

The survey instrument was developed by the researcher with the use of the previous studies that were aligned with the statement of the problem. It underwent validation process to ensure that all indicators were aligned with the given variables. This was given to the two sets of stakeholders namely: the internal and external stakeholders since this is a questionnaire which is in relation to the stakeholder’s involvement as correlate to school performance of School year 2022-2023.

Procedure

After the survey questionnaire was formulated, it was finalized, validated and printed for data gathering. Before it was distributed to the respondents, a letter to the OIC principal, and to the Schools Division Superintendent, was prepared and submitted to the Division office. It was received by the Human Resource Division for data processing for more than one week. Finally, it was approved, released, and endorsed to the OIC principal of Barangka Elementary School. The prepared questionnaire was distributed or released to the target respondents for data gathering thru google forms for those who could access the link and hard copy of survey questionnaire checklist for those who could not. These were accomplished by the respondents for one week span thru the initiative of the researcher together with the principal. She explained how to answer the different parts of the questionnaire properly thru the direction given and how to answer the different parts in order to get the desired data. After the questionnaires were answered, the result of the survey was completed and the data gathered passed through statistical treatment.

Results and Discussion

Extent of the Stakeholders Involvement in the Key School Programs as Perceived by Internal and External Stakeholders

Table 1. *Extent of Stakeholders’ Involvement in the Key School Programs as to Planning*

	<i>As a stakeholder, I....</i>			
	<i>Internal Stakeholders</i>		<i>Respondents</i>	
	<i>WM</i>	<i>VI</i>	<i>WM</i>	<i>VI</i>
1. Ask to help in defining the goals of the program/ project focused and based on the school vision and mission involving day-to-day challenges and keeping teachers and non-teaching staff active and cooperative.	3.18	ME	3.42	ME
2. Have the opportunity to get involved in the school improvement plans and planning school projects that will make the school academically friendly and reputable.	3.28	ME	3.45	ME
3. Participate in identifying the Priority Improvement Area formulating strategies and tracking implementation programs of school projects to reach a common educational goal through team effort because when multiple stakeholders are engaged, the team effort increases and the chances of success in reaching these goals is high.	3.22	ME	3.38	ME
4. Take part in gathering information that will help solve planning problems.	3.25	ME	3.35	ME
5. Assist in deciding if the school plan/ project design is sufficiently challenging to the school organization, consistent with organizational purpose, goals and objectives.	3.08	ME	3.37	ME
6. Get involved in developing alternative plans; Then agree to choose the one that is more feasible, realistic and likely to support objectives of the school projects	3.12	ME	3.42	ME
Overall Weighted Mean	3.19	ME	3.40	ME

This means that the extent of stakeholder’s involvement in planning as evident in the six ways or indicators was of moderate extent or limited since not all groups of stakeholders were properly represented in the implementation of school program. This finding implies that there is a need to motivate and strengthen their participation in planning by understanding and performing the listed functions or

indicators in table.

Table 2. *Extent of Stakeholders' Involvement in the Key School Programs as to Decision Making*

<i>As a stakeholder, I</i>	<i>Respondents</i>			
	<i>Internal Stakeholders</i>		<i>External Stakeholders</i>	
	<i>WM</i>	<i>VI</i>	<i>WM</i>	<i>VI</i>
1. Analyze that the stakeholder is crucial in decision-making process especially when the school is launching a new project, implementing a policy change, or resolving conflict.	3.18	ME	3.48	ME
2. Ask the school authorities to clearly define the decision that you are making/participating including its scope objectives and criteria. This will help you focus your stakeholder analysis on the relevant issues and avoid the unnecessary complexity.	3.18	ME	3.34	ME
3. Assist in gathering information related to decision-making requires information from many different sources that will help stakeholders identify difficult solutions to school problems related to the major programs and projects of the school.	3.20	ME	3.34	ME
4. Help in identifying the pros and cons of the issue and eliminating alternatives for the choices by weighing the evidence option from the pros and cons first. SWOT analysis and decision matrix.	3.15	ME	3.26	ME
5. Take time to help create an implementation plan that will put the project plan into action and monitor the program to determine whether or not their decision was a good one.	3.06	ME	3.25	ME
6. As part of the decision-makers representing the stakeholders, I get involved in the review of the decision made and its impact (both good and bad). If this solution made was not the best alternative, we will quickly adapt changes, and make decisions with the resources we have.	3.09	ME	3.28	ME
Overall Weighted Mean	3.15	ME	3.32	ME

It is manifested in the result that there was cooperation that took place in the decision making at a moderate extent as shown in performing the different roles listed in the table but only few of them were able to participate because not all groups were properly represented and only some were chosen to participate. From the result, it implies that some were not really tapped to involve in decision making and if given the chance their involvement was limited.

Table 3. *Extent of Stakeholders' Involvement in the Key School Programs as to Implementation*

<i>As a stakeholder, I....</i>	<i>Respondents</i>			
	<i>Internal Stakeholders</i>		<i>External Stakeholders</i>	
	<i>WM</i>	<i>VI</i>	<i>WM</i>	<i>VI</i>
1. Familiarize myself with the school issue on programs/project so I will know precisely what decision to make.	3.37	ME	3.48	ME
2. Review relevant information as aid in my decision and/or action.	3.29	ME	3.42	ME
3. Think about possible alternatives by listing possibilities, by asking questions and listening to feedback from after concerned stakeholders.	3.22	ME	3.43	ME
4. Weigh collected evidence by reviewing the possible wins and losses that could experience for each possible alternative.	3.15	ME	3.29	ME
5. Made a decision by trusting myself that I am prepared to make the call/decision	3.20	ME	3.23	ME
6. Assist the school in sourcing out funds for students to be able to participate in academic and non-academic competition by submitting my plans to the team of decision-makers and help create a plan that sets the school program/project to succeed by making sure that the project will give benefits to the learners	3.02	ME	3.31	ME
Overall Weighted Mean	3.21	ME	3.36	ME

This means that the two groups of respondents were involved by performing the six indicators as enumerated in the table. The findings implies that the two groups of respondents have limited participation since only were few of them who have really the chance to be involved fully that there is still a need for them to be involved.

Table 4. *Extent of the Stakeholders' Involvement in the Key School Programs as to Information Dissemination*

<i>As a stakeholder, I.....</i>	<i>Respondents</i>			
	<i>Internal Stakeholders</i>		<i>External Stakeholders</i>	
	<i>WM</i>	<i>VI</i>	<i>WM</i>	<i>VI</i>
1. Actively attend the school dissemination-program by participating in meetings and conferences relative to important announcement about new school policies, newly created programs and projects and help relay this information to stakeholders.	3.26	ME	3.38	ME
2. Volunteer in the different school projects and activities by announcing or giving out the good news to the stakeholders and community via the social media and traditional media.	3.12	ME	3.28	ME

3. Spearhead and actively participated in the cleanliness and maintenance like Brigada Eskwela Programs by extending some needed resources (i.e. financial, material, and labor)	3.29	ME	3.45	ME
4. Help convince civic community-minded members to extend assistance to the school during special activities like teachers' month, school foundation anniversary, scouting week, sports fest and other special activities.	3.20	ME	3.34	ME
5. Respond positively to the call or request of the school authorities relative to urgent activities that needs the presence of stakeholders; participation such as coming of Dep Ed Officials and government dignitaries interested in evaluating and observing the school-based management.	3.28	ME	3.35	ME
Overall Weighted Mean	3.23	ME	3.36	ME

This means that as stakeholder, they should also be tapped to involve themselves in information dissemination so that this will lead to a higher extent of stakeholders. involvement especially if all are properly informed about the projects of the school.

Table 5. *Extent of Stakeholders' Involvement in the Key School Programs as to Engagement Strategy*

<i>As a stakeholder, I.....</i>	<i>Respondents</i>			
	<i>Internal Stakeholders</i>		<i>External Stakeholders</i>	
	<i>WM</i>	<i>VI</i>	<i>WM</i>	<i>VI</i>
1. Inform /update the school on the development of various programs, projects and activities of the school or vice versa.	3.15	ME	3.32	ME
2. Consult by the school management when they are seeking feedback, opinions, suggestions and they consider views in their school decision-making process.	3.06	ME	3.32	ME
3. Involve myself to the school by sharing my valuable knowledge, experience and perspective that can significantly enhance the school projects on time thru brainstorming, feed backing, problem-solving and generating ideas in constant communication throughout the project cycle.	3.25	ME	3.32	ME
4. Collaborate with other stakeholders of the school with high level of interest, commitment and influence in the school project by being an active partner in decision-making, and their input is given equal weight alongside other factors.	3.25	ME	3.35	ME
5. Engage in meaningful volunteer work in our school (i.e., value formation activity, sports competition) that enhances positive interactions encouraging the youth.	3.28	ME	3.42	ME
Overall Weighted Mean	3.20	ME	3.35	ME

It can be gleaned that both groups of respondents were involved in school programs but only to a limited extent. Only selected stakeholders had the chance to perform the different engagement strategies as enumerated in the table.

Thus, if all stakeholders are properly represented to participate in engagement strategy therefore, this may lead to a higher extent of involvement.

Table 6. *Extent of the Stakeholders' Involvement in the Key School Programs as to Evaluation*

<i>As a stakeholder, I.....</i>	<i>Respondents</i>			
	<i>Internal Stakeholders</i>		<i>External Stakeholders</i>	
	<i>WM</i>	<i>VI</i>	<i>WM</i>	<i>VI</i>
1. Collaborate with school team/group of stakeholders relative to clear understanding of the objectives, scope, and timeline of the school project in order to set a realistic expectation, allocate resources efficiently and monitor program effectively.	3.22	ME	3.34	ME
2. Assess the current status of the project by regularly examining the project program in relation to its goals, timeline, and budget.	3.09	ME	3.23	ME
3. Maintain open communication with our team/group of stakeholders during monitoring and evaluating phase which is crucial for staying on track and addressing any concerns.	3.29	ME	3.31	ME
4. Analyze the results achieved by the school project by continuously evaluating the school project's performance based on the current results against the project grade.	3.08	ME	3.37	ME
5. Provide timely feedback whether the school programs/projects are achieving their objectives and in line with community needs and desires. Thus, Monitoring and Evaluation team of the school helps those involved with any type of projects to asses if progress desired is being achieved.	3.15	ME	3.26	ME
Overall Weighted Mean	3.17	ME	3.30	ME

This implies that the two groups of stakeholders performed in a limited basis. Only few of them collaborated with school team/group of stakeholders to have the chance to evaluate as performed in the five listed ways of involvement

Therefore, with this kind of situation there is really a need to engage all groups of stakeholders so that they will be properly represented thru the representative or leaders of each group so that these will be properly disseminated and to be put into action that may enhance the performance or extent of involvement of stakeholders.

Significant Difference Between the Perceptions of the Two Groups of Stakeholder Respondents on the Extent of Their Involvement in the Cited Key School Programs with Regard to the Different Aspects

Table 7. *Test of Significant Difference in the Perception of the Two Groups of Respondents on the Extent of the Stakeholders' Involvement in the Key School Programs regarding Planning*

Respondents	n	OWM	s	Computed z Value	Critical z value	Decision	Interpretation
Internal Stakeholders	65	3.19	0.64	1.81	1.96	Fail to reject the H ₀	Not Significant
Eternal Stakeholders	65	3.40	0.68				

It is evident in the table that the computed z value (1.81) was lower than the critical z value (1.96). Hence, at a 5% level of significance, the statistical decision was not to reject the null hypothesis. This implies that there was no significant difference between the perceptions of the two groups of respondents on the extent of the stakeholders' involvement in the Key School Programs pertaining to planning.

Table 8. *Test of Significant Difference in the Perception of the Two Groups of Respondents on the Extent of the Stakeholders' Involvement in the Key School Programs regarding Decision Making*

Respondents	n	OWM	s	Computed z Value	Critical z value	Decision	Interpretation
Internal Stakeholders	65	3.15	0.56	1.75	1.96	Fail to reject the H ₀	Not Significant
Eternal Stakeholders	65	3.32	0.55				

According to the table, the computed z value (1.75) was less than the critical z value (1.96). Thus, at a 5% level of significance the statistical decision was to fail to reject the null hypothesis. This concludes that there was no significant difference between the perceptions of the two groups of respondents on the extent of the stakeholders' involvement in the Key School Programs pertaining to decision making.

Table 9. *Test of Significant Difference in the Perception of the Two Groups of Respondents on the Extent of the Stakeholders' Involvement in the Key School Programs regarding Information Dissemination*

Respondents	n	OWM	s	Computed z Value	Critical z value	Decision	Interpretation
Internal Stakeholders	65	3.21	0.55	1.58	1.96	Fail to reject the H ₀	Not Significant
Eternal Stakeholders	65	3.36	0.53				

From the table, the computed z value (1.58) was smaller than the critical z value (1.96). Hence, the statistical decision was not to reject the null hypothesis at a 5% level of significance. This supports that there was no significant difference between the perceptions of the two groups of respondents on the extent of the stakeholders' involvement in the Key School Programs pertaining to information dissemination.

Table 10. *Test of Significant Difference in the Perception of the Two Groups of Respondents on the Extent of the Stakeholders' Involvement in the Key School Programs regarding Information Dissemination*

Respondents	n	OWM	s	Computed z Value	Critical z value	Decision	Interpretation
Internal Stakeholders	65	3.23	0.54	1.42	1.96	Fail to reject the H ₀	Not Significant
Eternal Stakeholders	65	3.36	0.50				

As supported by the table, the computed z value (1.42) is below the critical z value (1.96). At a 5% significance level, this leads that the null hypothesis cannot be rejected. This implies that there is no significant difference between the perceptions of the two groups of respondents on the extent of the stakeholders' involvement in the Key School Programs pertaining to implementation.

Table 11. *Test of Significant Difference in the Perception of the Two Groups of Respondents on the Extent of the Stakeholders' Involvement in the Key School Programs regarding Engagement Strategy*

Respondents	n	OWM	s	Computed z Value	Critical z value	Decision	Interpretation
Internal Stakeholders	65	3.20	0.59	1.49	1.96	Fail to reject the H ₀	Not Significant
Eternal Stakeholders	65	3.35	0.56				

As depicted in the table, the computed z value (1.49) was lesser than the critical z value (1.96). So, the statistical decision was not to reject the null hypothesis at a 5% level of significance. This indicates that there was no significant difference between the perceptions of the two groups of respondents on the extent of the stakeholders' involvement in the Key School Programs pertaining to engagement strategy.

It is specified in the table 12 that the computed z value (1.32) was lower than the critical z value (1.96). Therefore, at a 5% significance level this indicates that the null hypothesis could not be rejected. This shows that there was no significant difference between the perceptions of the two groups of respondents on the extent of the stakeholders' involvement in the Key School Programs pertaining to

evaluation.

Table 12. *Test of Significant Difference in the Perception of the Two Groups of Respondents on the Extent of the Stakeholders 'Involvement in the Key School Programs regarding Evaluation*

Respondents	n	OWM	s	Computed z Value	Critical z value	Decision	Interpretation
Internal Stakeholders	65	3.17	0.53	1.32	1.96	Fail to reject the H ₀	Not Significant
Eternal Stakeholders	65	3.30	0.59				

Considering the result of the performance level of Barangka Elementary school as perceived by the internal and external stakeholders on the access to inclusive education and marginalized group, having an overall weighted mean of 3.62 and 3.53 respectively means that the access to inclusive education and the marginalized group were highly evident, therefore the school should maintain this thru the stakeholders' involvement which can be maintained by promoting stakeholders' engagement program.

Table 13. *Level of School Performance of Barangka Elementary School with Respect to Access*

Indicators	Respondents			
	Internal Stakeholders		External Stakeholders	
	WM	VI	WM	VI
A. Level of School's Access to Inclusive Education				
The school...				
1. Provides educational services for all students including those with special needs.	3.69	HE	3.63	HE
2. "No child is left behind policy" provides all children with a fair, equal, and significant opportunity to obtain a high-quality education.	3.78	HE	3.60	HE
3. Learners are all enrolled in school and learning centers.	3.75	HE	3.72	HE
4. Supports the collection of dis aggregate data by disability for emergency response and/or monitoring to help with tailored interventions, leading to improved support for children with disabilities in their learning environment.	3.57	HE	3.52	HE
5. Access programs are responsive to the needs of their learners and consistent with their interests and aptitudes which is also evident in different contest or activities they are joining inside and outside the school campus.	3.59	HE	3.52	HE
6. Considers a variety of student characteristics, including ethnic background, race, abilities, disabilities, age, gender, language abilities and preferred learning style.	3.63	HE	3.57	HE
7. Removes barriers to learning before they can affect anyone by providing them with environment conducive to learning and with sufficient equipment and facilities.	3.51	HE	3.43	ME
B. Level of School's Access to Reaching the Marginalized				
The school...				
1. Analyzes data to identify gaps in student support and ensure that programs designed for marginalized students are having the desired impact just like the Project HEART(reduced dropout Rates) and Project LEARN(reduced non-reader pupils)and GATES(Gain Agility in transforming Effective Teaching Strategies)necessary for Quality Instructions.	3.54	HE	3.54	HE
2. Provides high priority resources to its most marginalized children which is evident in the Feeding program, CAFESIDAD,ALS and other beneficiaries of programs.	3.66	HE	3.55	HE
3.Provides details on operationalizing the continuous learning delivery thru asynchronous and synchronous sessions/online or modular and face to face classes from the start of school year 2022-2023 until it ended.	3.65	HE	3.51	HE
4.Has a unique plan of activities (practicing their skills at home with their parents and others) and follow up lessons or activities during the time for Face-to-face classes.	3.51	HE	3.43	ME
5. Has initiated programs, projects, and activities (PPAs) under the umbrella of DepEd PPAs. such as Brigada Eskwela, Brigada Pagbasa and WINS.	3.63	HE	3.49	ME
6.Provides support to education systems to ensure that distance learning is accessible during suspension of classes and as it migrates to full face to face classes.	3.71	HE	3.54	HE
7.Conducts home visitation with peer tutoring following health and safety protocols to students who do not have gadgets and anyone at home who is capable of guiding them in learning and those who are at risk of dropping out.	3.55	HE	3.45	ME
8.Uses of gadgets in reaching academically struggling students and pupils with different problems.	3.48	ME	3.45	ME
Overall Weighted Mean	3.62	HE	3.53	HE

With the result of the study in table 14, it implies that the performance of the school depends on how the stakeholders involved themselves in the key School programs of the school or how they experienced the indicators listed in the table in reality. Therefore, there is a need for both internal stakeholders and external stakeholders to be involved in the different aspects like planning, decision making, information dissemination, implementation, engagement strategy, and evaluation of projects thru the proposed engagement program in order that the performance of the school will be highly evident.

Table 14. *Level of School Performance of Barangka Elementary School with respect to Quality*

Indicators	Respondents			
	Internal Stakeholders		External Stakeholders	
	WM	VI	WM	VI
A. Level of School's Quality to Teaching and Learning Process				
The school...				
1. Has learning delivery modality based on students' classification and condition and other school programs and activities.	3.62	HE	3.60	HE
2. Adjusts on teachers' teaching load assignment based on their capabilities.	3.40	ME	3.52	HE
3. Prepares a flexible weekly home learning plan which is based on standards.	3.66	HE	3.51	HE
4. Communicates the Content, Purpose, and use of Weekly Home Learning Plan to the learners and parents thru Messenger or Group Chat or Facebook page.	3.65	HE	3.55	HE
5. Capacitates teachers by providing opportunities through attending different courses, in-service trainings, LAC sessions and webinars for their learning development and also reflected in Project GATES.	3.60	HE	3.52	HE
6. Conducts proper monitoring and evaluation of the chosen learning delivery modality throughout the school year.	3.49	ME	3.58	HE
7. Employs Multi-modal Assessment to account for the diverse needs of the students and the requirements set by the learning delivery modalities.	3.46	ME	3.49	ME
8. Supervises and monitors the learners' progress and, if necessary, shall provide remediation and enhancement.	3.63	HE	3.51	HE
B. Level of Schools' Quality to Provision of Learning Resources				
The school...				
1. Has complete distribution and retrieval of SLMs, WHLPs and ILMPs.	3.43	ME	3.45	ME
2. Adopts distance learning mode and is provided with modules printed or digital.	3.60	HE	3.51	HE
3. Has an appropriate acquisition of online and offline learning	3.55	HE	3.48	ME
4. Provides tablets, other gadgets, and loads to selected pupils	3.18	ME	3.09	ME
5. Provides soft and hard copies of materials for school-initiated learning interventions in all subject areas.	3.46	ME	3.43	ME
Overall Weighted Mean	3.52	HE	3.48	ME

Lastly based on the data in the table 15, the level of performance of schools' governance to education financing as perceived by the stakeholders was moderately evident which was shown in the weighted mean of the different indicators. The findings imply that all groups of stakeholders must be involved so that that the performance under the governance which were already Highly Evident can be maintained and those which were Moderately Evident will be improved.

Table 15. *Level of School Performance of Barangka Elementary School with respect to Governance*

Indicators	Respondents			
	Internal Stakeholders		External Stakeholders	
	WM	VI	WM	VI
A. Level of Schools' Governance to Safe Operations				
The school...				
1. Provides a safe working environment for employees as well as a safe learning environment for student.	3.62	HE	3.54	HE
2. Conducts regular faculty meetings and Online Kamustahan in preparation for the distribution and retrieval of learning materials.	3.51	HE	3.37	ME
3. Implements alternative work arrangement for both teaching and non-teaching personnel.	3.62	HE	3.51	HE
4. Uses distance learning to ensure that education continues without jeopardizing the students' lives.	3.58	HE	3.49	ME
5. Has online facilitation of documents and use of Google Drives to manage operations	3.62	HE	3.54	HE
6. Complies to DO. No. 40, s.2012 (Policy Guidelines on Protecting Children in School from Abuse, Violence, Exploitation, Discrimination, Bullying and Other forms of Abuse)	3.63	HE	3.51	HE
7. Considers the Safe Assessment procedures of learning.	3.58	HE	3.54	HE
B. Level of Schools' Governance to Well-being, Resilience and Protection				
The school...				
1. Conducts symposiums and conferences that encourage positivity among learners and school staff during the pandemic, during and after disaster or emergencies and they also be safe and protected from risks and impacts from natural and human induced hazards thru project ALERT.	3.51	HE	3.43	ME
2. Continues to promote health and wellness among its students thru the project GATAS at ZUMBA (For unhealthy and malnourished children) and WINS(clean and safe school environment and correct hygiene and sanitation practices among learners)	3.34	ME	3.46	ME

3.Provides and promotes training and webinars on Mental Health and Cyber bullying.	3.38	ME	3.43	ME
4. Safety, Work Ethics, etc. through School Learning Action Cells (SLAC)	3.55	HE	3.46	ME
5.Coordinates with the related agencies that can assist in the promotion of healthy life among the learners, teaching, and non-teaching personnel.	3.54	HE	3.45	ME
C. Level of Schools' Governance to Education Financing				
The school...				
1. Provides a budget for the procurement of additional Gadgets, materials, Facilities and SLMs as the school year's enrollment increases.	3.31	ME	3.40	ME
2.Provides budget for the procurement of office supplies for the printing and reproduction of Learning Activity Sheets and Learning Task Sheets.	3.37	ME	3.35	ME
3. Strengthens partnership with private institutions, business/industry sector NGOs for sponsorship and donation.	3.34	ME	3.46	ME
Overall Weighted Mean	3.50	HE	3.46	ME

Significant Correlation Between the Extent of the Internal and External stakeholders' Involvement in the School Programs and School Performance

Table 16. *Test of Significant Correlation Between the Stakeholders' Involvement in the School Programs and School Performance as to Access*

Variables	Pearson r	Strength	Computed t Value	Critical t Value	Decision	Interpretation
Planning Access	0.47	Moderate	6.02	1.98	Reject the H ₀	Significant
Decision Making Access	0.52	Moderate	6.89	1.98	Reject the H ₀	Significant
Information Dissemination Access	0.51	Moderate	6.71	1.98	Reject the H ₀	Significant
Implementation Access	0.61	Moderate	8.71	1.98	Reject the H ₀	Significant
Engagement Strategy Access	0.55	Moderate	7.45	1.98	Reject the H ₀	Significant
Evaluation Access	0.49	Moderate	6.36	1.98	Reject the H ₀	Significant

There was` a significant correlation between the stakeholders' involvement in the school programs and school performance as regards Access. There is evidence to conclude that the higher the extent of stakeholders' involvement in school programs, the higher the level of school performance in terms of access. When more people like parents, teachers, and community members get involved in school activities, it tends to boost the school's performance and makes it more accessible.

Table 17. *Test of Significant Correlation Between the Stakeholders' Involvement in the School Programs and School Performance as to Quality*

Variables	Pearson r	Strength	Computed t Value	Critical t Value	Decision	Interpretation
Planning Quality	0.51	Moderate	6.71	1.98	Reject the H ₀	Significant
Decision Making Quality	0.52	Moderate	6.89	1.98	Reject the H ₀	Significant
Information Dissemination Quality	0.51	Moderate	6.71	1.98	Reject the H ₀	Significant
Implementation Quality	0.56	Moderate	7.65	1.98	Reject the H ₀	Significant
Engagement Strategy Quality	0.56	Moderate	7.65	1.98	Reject the H ₀	Significant
Evaluation Quality	0.50	Moderate	6.53	1.98	Reject the H ₀	Significant

This suggests that there is a significant correlation between the stakeholders' involvement in the school programs and school performance as regards Quality. There is evidence to conclude that the higher the extent of stakeholders' involvement in school programs, the higher the level of school performance in terms of quality. This implies that the performance of the school is a result of stakeholders' involvement, thus, there is a need for all stakeholders to be well-motivated to participate.

There was a significant correlation between the stakeholders' involvement in the school programs and school performance as regards Governance. There is evidence to conclude that the higher the extent of stakeholders' involvement in school programs, the higher the

level of school performance in terms of governance.

Table 18. *Test of Significant Correlation Between the Stakeholders' Involvement in the School Programs and School Performance as to Governance*

Variables	Pearson r	Strength	Computed Value	Critical Value	Decision	Interpretation
Planning Governance	0.47	Moderate	6.02	1.98	Reject the H ₀	Significant
Decision Making Governance						
Information Dissemination Governance	0.53	Moderate	7.07	1.98	Reject the H ₀	Significant
Implementation Governance						
Engagement Strategy Governance	0.50	Moderate	6.53	1.98	Reject the H ₀	Significant
Evaluation Governance						
	0.45	Moderate	5.70	1.98	Reject the H ₀	Significant

Challenges Encountered by the Internal and External Stakeholders in the Implementation of the School Programs as Perceived by the Two Groups of Respondents

Table 19. *Challenges Encountered by the Stakeholders in the Implementation of the School Programs*

Challenges	f	R
Open dialogue about challenges and solutions for school	40	1
Capitalizing on the financial assets of community partners and funding streams to support programs and activities aligned with their common vision	37	2
Lack of stakeholders' participation in school-initiated programs and projects	35	3.5
Sourcing of project funds	35	3.5
Not invited in planning and of school projects.	33	5
Not involved in decision-making of proposed school projects.	31	6
Lack of collaboration between the schoolteachers and parents.	28	7
Poor dissemination of school announcements like meetings and other school activities from school authorities.	27	8.5
Presenting project reports to the stakeholders	27	8.5
Not involved in monitoring and evaluation of projects.	25	10
Raising the commitment of involvement to school activities	24	11
Directing and motivating stakeholders to be involved in school activities	23	12
Inability of school personnel to influence outside stakeholders	17	13
Not involved / invited to help in information dissemination of school projects and activities.	14	14.5
Resistance of stakeholders towards educational innovation and programs	14	14.5

The top five challenges commonly encountered by the internal and external stakeholders in the implementation of the school programs were: 1) Open dialogue about the challenges/obstacles encountered and solutions needed in the implementation of school program (rank 1). 2.) Capitalizing on the financial assets of community partners and funding streams to support programs and activities aligned with their common vision. (rank 2). 3.) Lack of stakeholders' participation in school-initiated programs and projects (3.5) and 4.) Sourcing of project funds (rank 3.5).5.) Not invited in planning and dissemination of school projects. (rank 5) and the remaining challenges are interrelated to each other.

Proposed Intervention Program

Based on the findings of the study, an intervention program was deemed necessary, hence, was proposed in this study.

Rationale

The performance of the school depends on the result of the implementation of the different projects and programs reflected in the School Improvement Plan which are evident in the different indicators such as access, quality and governance and in the different

activities where the different stakeholders engaged in like planning, decision making, information dissemination, implementation, engagement strategy and evaluation.

The school cannot do it alone. There is a need to cooperate and collaborate with the different stakeholders as mentioned in the latest study in order to implement the different project and programs of the school towards the attainment of the school's mission, vision and goals. Just what Saxene(2014) believed that the involvement of the broader community of the school, improved communication and public understanding and allowed the incorporation of the perspectives, experiences and expertise of participating community members to improve or refine proposals, strategies and process. According to him, the involvement of the broader community of a school leads to higher performance and school improvement.

Based from the findings of the study that the stakeholders as respondents have minimal involvement in the programs and projects of the school in the different activities where stakeholders need to be involved, they both share similar views that they both have moderate extent of involvement, the school is performing well in terms of access, quality and governance and they experienced challenges along the way, this stakeholders Engagement Program was proposed

Since the School Governing Council is the highest governing body that operates under the principle that education is a shared responsibility and accountability among school community stakeholders., therefore, it is stated in its function that it has the right to produce stable and effective leadership which strengthen achievement of the school's objective and which is sensitive to guard the vision and values of the past while being responsive to changes in community values and the preferences of the immediate stakeholders.

Objectives

The Proposed Stakeholders Engagement Program aims:

To raise the awareness of the stakeholders of their vital role in the implementation of school program, projects, and activities.

To motivate the stakeholders to get involved and collaborate with one another for the successful implementation of school programs, projects and activities.

To enhance and sustain the effective and quality performance of the stakeholders in school programs, projects and activities.

To promote school - community partnership through active engagement of stakeholders towards the successful attainment of the vision, mission and goals of the academic institutions

Designate stakeholders who will represent their group in the Stakeholders Engagement Program those who can help in the implementation of school program which will be done during the planning which is initiated by the school head as the leader of the School Governing Council and the head of the School Project Team responsible for the implementation of the implementation of the School Improvement Plan.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of this study, the following are the conclusions drawn from the results of the study.

The stakeholders used as respondents of the study have minimal involvement in the programs of the subject school relative to its activities such as planning, decision making, implementation, information dissemination, engagement strategy, and evaluation.

The two groups of respondents share similar views on the stakeholders' extent of involvement in the program of the subject school.

The subject school perform well in terms of access, quality, and governance.

The stakeholders' involvement in the programs of the subject school has bearing on the performance of the school in terms of criteria-access, quality, and governance.

The stakeholders experience problems in the implementation of school programs.

An intervention program, specifically, "Stakeholders Engagement Program" was deemed necessary for the effective end quality performance of Barangka Elementary School.

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